

Opportunities to combat loneliness: How care facilities are connecting neighborhoods

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Society is getting older. Against the backdrop of the challenges posed by this demographic change and the increasing number of older people, new ideas are needed for designing good, livable living environments and neighborhoods. The issue of loneliness is becoming particularly relevant in this context. More and more facilities are therefore developing innovative offerings to strengthen social and digital participation and position themselves as open, connected places in the neighborhood.

Care facilities in transition

Many older people are no longer able to take advantage of local offerings, such as games or neighborhood meeting places due to limited mobility, illness, or bad weather. The coronavirus pandemic in particular has highlighted how quickly such social offerings can disappear. Community centers remained closed, and social gatherings were rare. The result: loneliness increases.

Care facilities are therefore also facing new challenges: it is no longer just about care in the traditional sense, but also about how to reach older people who live alone or hardly ever leave their homes. [Some organizations are already implementing concrete measures to counteract the challenge of loneliness in neighborhoods](#). In addition to in-person services, they also offer opportunities to acquire digital skills. Some are launching pilot projects, such as training courses with tablets and online content specifically tailored to older people (cf. Deutsches Institut für Sozialwirtschaft e.V., 2022).

This is fundamentally changing the role of some care facilities. Although human and financial resources are scarce, care providers are considering what role they themselves could play after the pandemic and how they could promote digital participation. They are no longer just places for people in need of care, but could increasingly develop into places of community, so-called third places, that are partly accessible to the entire neighborhood and its people of all ages.

What are third places?

The term “third places” was coined by American sociologist Ray Oldenburg. In 1989, he described how important social meeting places are disappearing in modern societies because life is increasingly concentrated at home (first place) and at work (second place). He therefore advocated for the restoration of community-building places, known as third places. These are public or semi-public places where people can meet regardless of their origin, age, or social status, such as cafés, bookstores, hair salons, or libraries. Oldenburg saw them as a central building block for social cohesion and quality of life because they offer opportunities for spontaneous encounters, conversations, and shared experiences (cf. Oldenburg, 1999). According to the Körber Foundation (2024), the definition is even broader today: “[Third](#)

[places are spaces or places that bring as many people together as possible and enable exchange without the pressure to consume. They are meeting places for a diverse society.](#)” This includes not only classic places such as cafés or libraries, but also new formats: neighborhood centers, cultural centers, or shared spaces in rural areas or care facilities that are periodically open to the neighborhood. Care facilities are thus increasingly seen as part of a social infrastructure that enables belonging, dialogue, and social participation.

Against loneliness and for digital participation in old age

Such meeting places already exist. They are supported by low-threshold offers from the neighborhood and by volunteer work. They function as third places that specifically combat loneliness and strengthen social participation in old age. In the project [Against loneliness and for digital participation in old age GETA International](#)), for example, we spoke with some of the people involved in the new hybrid meeting centers: “We are a traditional diaconal organization, a small ‘Konsum’-store. We offer every service you can imagine!” says the director of a care facility in Cottbus, describing the variety of existing and planned services in the neighborhood. Many facilities have moved in this direction and have established or expanded regular meetings, learning cafés, and tea afternoons to promote exchange among residents, but also among potential future residents, relatives, and neighbors. There is demand for these services in the neighborhood: “Sometimes the whole family asks about them. (...) We are seen as experts. We do this as part of our work with relatives,” says a representative of a large care provider in Stuttgart. Her care facility is increasingly becoming a hub in the neighborhood—a place to go in everyday life, a place of trust, and a center of expertise that goes far beyond traditional care.

Digital bridges between Berlin and California

The issue of loneliness is becoming an increasing problem not only among the aging population, but also among younger generations. Studies show that loneliness affects different generations and genders in different ways. Women age 70 and above and men between the ages of 40 and 60 are particularly affected, however, studies also show an alarming increase in loneliness among young adults age 18 to 29. These figures indicate that there will be an even greater need in the future to combat loneliness in a targeted manner across all generations. Demographic change, characterized by a decline in birth rates and an increasing number of very elderly people (85+) by 2030, suggests that loneliness could continue to increase among older people (cf. Kaspar et al., 2022; cf. Huxhold & Engstler, 2019).

A care facility cannot meet the growing need for help and support services, for example through a staffed reception desk. However, many facilities have rooms that can be used for open neighborhood services. This could create contact points that link digital networks and analog services and promote social interaction. A mix of digital and analog services ensures that people can stay involved. Even if, for example, they are unable to leave the house due to weather conditions or are temporarily immobile.

The Eighth Ageing Report Commission (2020) emphasizes that digital technologies have the potential to improve the lives of older people, especially when they help maintain social relationships, for example

with relatives or caregivers. [“In the best case scenario, digital technologies \(e.g., in the form of voice assistants\) can significantly expand existing communication options and thus help to overcome loneliness”](#) (cf. *ibid.*, 123). Teaching digital skills is playing an increasingly important role. Some care facilities are using innovative approaches to promote digital skills and thus enable social participation. “We’re not going to become an Elon Musk satellite home, but we’re going to introduce communication technology in some way,” said one facility manager. In this context, however, it is important that digital technologies do not in turn lead to increased feelings of loneliness. A strong connection to care facilities and personal contact with caregivers is still important, because it can be supportive in this regard.

What is GETA International?

In Germany, too, companies and start-ups are committed to sustainably improving the living conditions and health of older people through the use of digital technologies.

The project [GETA International](#) identifies these companies and is establishing a learning and development network between players in the social, health, and technology sectors in the greater Berlin area and companies in California. This network enables structured and continuous exchange between the two regions in order to improve the living conditions of older people through innovative digital solutions. Within the framework of GETA International, the participating companies and institutions gain rapid access to validated innovations, technical expertise, best practice examples, and evaluation results from the other region. This cross-border transfer of knowledge and experience promotes the joint, international, and interdisciplinary development of new products and services. At the same time, it provides new impetus for internationalization and significantly strengthens the expansion potential of Berlin-based companies. GETA International is part of the Internationalization Program (Pfl-NETZ), which is funded by the Senate Department for Economics, Energy, and Public Enterprises (SENWiEnBe) with funds from the European Union. It is also part of the Berlin initiative, Berlin goes International, with which the capital city aims to increase its international visibility and attractiveness for founders from all over the world.

Connecting the community, but how?

In the best-case scenario—as pioneers in the US have shown—the social economy, technology companies, and other supporters such as research institutions like [CITRIS Health](#) or other civil society initiatives work hand in hand. A pilot project in the Märkisch-Oderland district, co-initiated by GETA International, shows how such collaborations can be implemented in practice. A care provider there has managed to tackle loneliness among the elderly in the district with a large project volume from the Federal Ministry for Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth (BMFSFJ). “We had to get people out of their homes, that’s the problem,” says the head of the loneliness project. They have succeeded in Märkisch-Oderland by offering continuous activities at the local neighborhood meeting place. In addition to sports and cultural activities, there are plenty of breaks for conversation over a cup of tea or coffee. “We won’t reach everyone, which is also painful. (...) The barrier to participation is sometimes very high, especially among seniors.” The project provides tablets to older people who are affected by loneliness or immobility, so

that they cannot take advantage of the on-site services offered by the care facility. The content on the tablet is provided by [Active at Home](#) in Berlin. Active at Home specializes in offering programs to seniors that promote culture, exercise, and social interaction. Meanwhile, [Televisit](#), a non-profit organization from the US, has developed an intuitive platform to enable seniors to easily participate in online courses and discussion groups, even if they have no prior digital knowledge. The intuitive system significantly lowers the barriers to entry. Televisit offers an easy-to-use app that is installed on a tablet and focuses exclusively on one function – it “calls” as soon as an event begins. The tablet then rings like a telephone. Users have a choice: accept the call (“I’m in!”) or reject it (“I’m not in!”). The common goal of Televisit and the Active at Home project is to better reach seniors living alone who are on the verge of needing care and to give them easy access to social services. This is intended not only to reduce loneliness, but also to improve physical and mental health. The project, which was launched in June 2024, is currently in a pilot phase. The aim of this phase is to gain a better understanding of the needs and requirements of the target group.

However, the implementation of such projects and the expanded role of care facilities in connecting with the neighborhood often come up against financial constraints. The additional tasks, such as serving as a place of learning for digital skills, require resources that go beyond traditional care financing. “We can't afford to hire people or create jobs. As a non-profit organization, we are almost completely dependent on subsidized areas,” says the director of a care facility in Cottbus, describing the tense situation. In order to realize new offerings nonetheless, many facilities are looking for creative financing models – for example, through new partnerships with service providers and universities.

Combating loneliness requires innovative approaches that combine social proximity and digital participation. Projects such as GETA International, committed care facilities, and technology-savvy companies show how cooperation can lead to viable solutions. In such neighborhoods, digital interaction becomes a living reality – across generations, locally anchored, and internationally networked. It requires joint efforts, partnership structures, and a supportive infrastructure. Only by activating these analog and digital services, can a strong network be created that leaves no one behind.

References

- Deutsches Institut für Sozialwirtschaft e.V. (2022, 30. November). *50 Millionen Euro gegen Einsamkeit*.
www.seniorenpolitik-aktuell.de. <https://www.seniorenpolitik-aktuell.de/50-millionen-euro-gegen-einsamkeit/>
- Die Achte Altersberichtscommission. (2020). Achter Altersbericht: Ältere Menschen und Digitalisierung.
In *Deutsches Zentrum für Altersfragen* (Bd. 19/21650)
[Report]. https://www.achter-altersbericht.de/fileadmin/altersbericht/pdf/aktive_PDF_Altersbericht_DT-Drucksache.pdf
- Huxhold, O. & Engstler, H. (2019). Soziale Isolation und Einsamkeit bei Frauen und Männern im Verlauf der zweiten Lebenshälfte. In *Springer eBooks* (S. 71–89). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-25079-9_5

- Kaspar, R., Wenner, J., & Tesch-Römer, C. (2022). *Einsamkeit in der Hochaltrigkeit*. (D80+ Kurzberichte, 4). Köln: Bundesministerium für Familie, Senioren, Frauen und Jugend; Universität zu Köln, Cologne Center for Ethics, Rights, Economics, and Social Sciences of Health (ceres); Deutsches Zentrum für Altersfragen. <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:0168-ssoar-77004-2>
- Körper-Stiftung. (2024). *Ein Haus für die Gemeinschaft*. <https://koerber-stiftung.de/projekte/begegnungsorte/ein-haus-fuer-die-gemeinschaft/>
- Oldenburg, R. (1999). *The great good place. Cafes, coffee shops, bookstores, bars, hair salons, and other hangouts at the heart of a community*. Marlowe & Company.